

Understanding the degradation process in zinc-iodine hybrid flow batteries

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1. Introduction

Stabilization of electricity grid is the compulsory step to fulfil the full potential of renewable energy sources. The most spread types of energy storage (ES) are physical-based and electrochemical-based ESs [1, 2]. Pumped hydro energy storage (PHES), compressed air and flywheel technologies are the representatives of physical-based ES, PHES being the most dominant among ES technologies, despite low flexibility, limited availability of suitable sites and high-investment costs. Li-ion batteries are the most dominant electrochemical ES technologies due to their high efficiency and energy density, nonetheless the high risk of fire and growing demand for the battery in e-mobility motivates R&D of alternative systems, incl. redox flow batteries (RFBs). The main advantages of RFBs are safety (non-flammability due to use of aqueous electrolytes) and flexible scalability (decoupled power and capacity) [3, 4]. So far, the vanadium redox flow battery (VRFB) represents the most developed system, which excels in long life-time (up to 15 000 cycles, 20 years), easy recyclability and residual cost of electrolytes. However, high capital expenditures (CAPEX) due to high vanadium price, low energy density hinder their commercialization. [5-10].

As an alternative, hybrid flow batteries (HFBs) with metal deposition are being developed due to their theoretically high energy density and abundant resources of metals such as zinc or iron. In this concept, the metal is being deposited on the negative electrode during battery charging, while it is being dissolved during the discharging. Thus, the volumetric capacity of HFB is given by two factors: the concentration of active species dissolved in the electrolytes, and by the molar amount of metal which can be deposited within the negative half-cell.

Various HFB chemistries have been reported. All-iron HFB excels in cost effectiveness of the active materials, low environmental impact and high safety. On the other hand, low redox potential of iron deposition promotes parasitic hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) on the negative electrode at relatively high rate, which is responsible for decreased coulombic efficiency and capacity loss due to faradaic imbalance between the electrolytes. Thus additional recombination cell is typically needed, which increases the complexity of the storage [11].

Zinc is another popular metal often used in HFBs, with various posolyte chemistries incl. zinc-air hybrid flow battery (ZAHFB), zinc-bromine hybrid flow battery (ZBHFB) or zinc-iodine hybrid flow battery (ZIHFB). Similarly to Fe-based systems, zinc-based HFB suffer from non-homogeneous metal deposition and dendrite formation, Zn corrosion and side reaction such as hydrogen evolution, which negatively influence efficiency and stability of those batteries [12]. While ZBHFB has the highest nominal OCV (1.85 V), relatively low cost of active species and high energy efficiency, its applicability is limited due to the toxicity and high volatility of Br₂. ZAHFB has slightly lower nominal OCV (1.65 V) and the uses of ambient air on the positive electrode make these batteries non-toxic and cost effective. However, poor efficiency and stability of positive electrodes together with the need for expensive electrocatalysis obstruct the commercialization of these batteries. ZIHFB has the lowest nominal OCV of 1.3 V, which is compensated by high volumetric capacity (ZnI₂ solubility goes up to 5 mol dm⁻³) with theoretical energy density of 167 Wh dm⁻³. Also the redox kinetics of iodine active species reaction on cheap carbon-based electrodes is faster compared to other halogen elements such as chlorine or bromine [13]. The electrode reaction including the standard redox potentials are stated below (see **equation 1-4**):

During the charging zinc is being deposited from solution (according to **equation 1**) and therefore Zn²⁺ concentration decreases in the negative electrolyte, while the reaction proceeds in the opposite direction during the battery discharge. In the positive half-cell I⁻ is being oxidized to low-soluble I₂ during the charging (see **equation 2**) which consequently complex with excess I⁻ to form I₃⁻ (see **equation 3**), thus only two third of iodine in electrolyte is used for the energy storage [13]. At higher states of charge (SoC) higher order polyiodides can be also formed. Jang et al. [14] reported that during the charging, a compact temporary I₂ film can be formed on the surface of the positive electrode, which significantly increases charge transfer resistance of the battery, which explains an observed increased cell overpotential by more than 300 mV at high current densities (>400 mA cm⁻²). The mentioned phenomenon can significantly limit the maximal operating power densities. In addition, I₃⁻ has a strong oxidizing strength, which enables fast dissolution of metallic zinc (self-discharge), according to **equation 5**:

Negative half-cell is linked with common limitations of zinc-based HFBs such as poor cyclability, non-homogenous zinc deposition (incl. dendrite formation), zinc oxidation and passivation by precipitated layer of zinc oxide or parasitic HER [15-17]. These challenges can be addressed differently, e.g., by optimizing hydrodynamics conditions of the flowing electrolyte [18], application of proprietary charging protocols (such as e.g., pulse interrupt current charging) [19] or by applying electrolyte additives [20, 21]. As already mentioned, the energy density of HFBs is not given only by solubility of active species but also by the amount of Zn which can be safely

deposited within the negative half-cell (in this manuscript, we will refer it to as areal capacity - Q_{areal}). Besides the negative half-cell geometry, Q_{areal} is influenced by the morphology of the deposited zinc, which can form three different morphologies: mossy (porous), crystalline (compact) and dendrite (needle-like) [17, 22]. Obviously, crystalline morphology is preferable due to the highest density and the best adhesion to the electrode substrate. The nature of morphology is known to be very dependent on the operating conditions (current density, electrolyte flow rate, bulk reactant concentration) affecting a thickness of diffusion layer close to electrode-electrolyte interface. According to Dundálek et al. [15] the morphology can be predicted by so-called current density ratio, CDR, i.e. ration of actual current to the limiting one. While low CDRs provide mossy structures, deposition close to limiting current densities promotes dendrite formation. It is worth to mention that a limiting current strongly depends on reactant concentration, flow conditions and temperature, thus optimal CDR can significantly vary during the cycling.

For the deposition planar substrate electrodes can be used, however, due to the limited mass transfer of the reactants (Zn^{2+}) to the electrode surface, 3D electrodes are more often used. The 3D electrode can be either metallic [23] or carbon-based [21, 24, 25], latter one being a common material in RFBs, typically in a form of a non-woven felt of graphitized polymeric fibres (graphite felt, GF). The 3D structure of GF increases the surface area available for the reaction, thus decreasing local current densities. However, with the GF electrode it can be expected that the deposited zinc is preferentially localized closer to the membrane/separator, when compared to the planar electrode due to higher (by one or two orders of magnitude) electronic conductivity of GF when compared to the ionic conductivity of electrolyte [21]. The deposition of zinc closer to the membrane/separator can lead to the faster penetration of zinc through the membrane causing and cell performance degradation due to the electric shortcut.

The choice of suitable electrode separator is a very important parameter in designing a flow battery cell/stack [26]. The separator is responsible for the mutual electronic separation of the negative and positive half-cells (preventing internal short-circuit), while it enables their ionic interconnection. In most RFB systems it also prevents mutual cross-contamination of the electrolytes. In principle, both porous separators and ion-exchange membranes (IEMs) can be used in ZIHFB. The porous separator, typically a thin polymeric film with small pores (units to tens μm) significantly reduces a convective flux of electrolytes between the individual half-cells, while it enables fast ionic transport for charge equalization during the battery operation. When compared to IEMs, however, its perm-selectivity is much lower which results in lower coulombic efficiency (CE) and faster capacity fade of battery operation due to active species cross-over. The worse ion selectivity of porous separators is compensated by typically much lower price and better mechanical and chemical stability over long operation time. The ionic conductivity of the separator soaked in a given electrolyte is mainly given by the pore structures, thickness [27].

IEMs are ion-selective typically polymeric separators with immobilized ionic functional groups in their structure and pore size in units of nano-meters, which yields in a preferential transport of either anions (in case of anion-exchange membranes (AEMs)) or cations (for cation exchange membranes (CEMs)). Battery performance can be optimized by tuning the membrane properties such as polarity of functional groups and their concentration (ion-exchange capacity, IEC),

chemical composition of the polymer (e.g. length of side-chains) or its thickness. Thinner membranes with high IEC are generally more suitable for efficient battery operation at high current densities enabling fast ionic transport but lower selectivity. [13, 26, 28].

In ZIHFB primarily use of CEMs has been reported, mostly Nafion by Chemours Company, as recently reviewed by Fan, D., et al. [13]. With CEMs, the cations from supporting electrolyte as well as Zn^{2+} ions can cross-over the membrane during the battery operation. The concentration of Zn^{2+} ions in the negolyte decreases significantly during the battery operation due to their conversion to metallic Zn (see **Figure S1b**). Thus, in case of miscible electrolytes (i.e. with same initial composition of both electrolytes), Zn^{2+} can permeate from posolyte due to the gradient of concentration. As the permselectivity of IEMs is never ideal, particularly in such highly concentrated electrolytes, the minor permeation of tri-iodide ions to negolyte and iodide ions to posolyte can also take place resulting in the reduced CE due to Zn oxidation (self-discharging, according to **eq. 5**).

Properties of separator used can significantly affect the battery performance and lifetime, particularly the issues related to internal short circuit caused by zinc dendrite growth during the battery charging, which is a common problem of zinc-based batteries. In general, larger pores of porous separators, when compared to IEMs, should simplify these degradation phenomena. Interestingly, Xie et al. [29] reported use of a polyolefin-based separator with high ion conductivity, showing a stable ZIHFB operation due to a so-called self-healing effect. This effect can be described as a self-discharge reaction of I_3^- with zinc dendrites that have grown into the pores of the separator, which results in the continuous dendrites dissolution (according to **eq. 5**) without deterioration of the battery performance, just for a price of lower CE . To further improve the ZIHFB, Xie et al. [30] manufactured a composite membrane by applying a thin layer of Nafion polymer on the previously used polyolefin porous separator to enhance perm-selectivity of the separator. Due to the application of thin Nafion layer the CE was increased by 11% when compared to the cell with pristine separator due to reduced I_3^- cross-over from posolyte. The single-cell with the composite membrane showed stable performance at 80 mA cm^{-2} for 500 cycles without any efficiency or capacity decay.

Kellamis et al. [21] demonstrated enhanced battery performance thanks to use of gluconate electrolyte additive together with the use of a non-conductive polymeric felt (NCF) on each side of the battery cell. The usage of NCF in the negative half-cell and addition of NCF to the positive one (combination of conductive GF and NCF on positive side) together with the use of the electrolyte additive led to the increased Q_{areal} from 60 mAh cm^{-2} (obtained with a standard flow battery construction) to 350 mAh cm^{-2} (at the beginning of the experiment, after 4 cycles the capacity was 280 mAh cm^{-2}) at current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} , with 53% voltaic efficiency (VE). Addition of potassium gluconate prevented the dendrites formation but, at the same time, decreased ionic conductivity of the electrolyte, which resulted in the decreased VE . More importantly, the presence of NCF in the positive half-cell prevented the formation of electric shorts caused by Zn dendrites. The battery of the same construction, but without the additive, achieved the initial Q_{areal} of 480 mAh cm^{-2} , however, after 8 cycles it dropped to 370 mAh cm^{-2} . Omission of the additive resulted in an increase of VE by approximately 8% under given conditions. The

authors demonstrated significant increase of available areal capacity for ZIHFB at reasonable current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} , that allows significant decrease of battery stack price.

ZIHFB shows great potential for highly effective and energetically dense stationary storage, and several recent publications showed a potential for successful scale-up. However, as Kellamis et al. [21] stated, commercialization of current ZIHFBs is still limited by low Q_{areal} of the negative battery half-cell. When the critical areal capacity (amount of the deposited Zn) is exceeded, battery is irreversibly damaged. This is typically accompanied by significant increase of ZIHFB cell overvoltage (eventually the presence of voltaic bulge) during the charging to higher Q_{areal} and it has been, to some extent, reported in literature [21, 31]. Voltaic bulge can be described as a sharp increase of battery overvoltage followed by its sudden drop upon further charging. In most reported cases, the voltaic bulge has not been achieved due to the limited charging voltage of battery operation but without an effort for deeper understanding of phenomena causing this overvoltage increase. In literature [21], the origin of the increased overvoltage is mostly related to increased mass transfer polarization, while the subsequent overvoltage drop is directly linked to the internal short-circuit of the battery by the deposited Zn [21]. However, to the best of our knowledge, no sufficiently detailed description of the degradation mechanism has been so-far provided and thus the voltaic bulge phenomenon is not yet fully understood, which complicates to design effective measures for enhancing performance, lifetime and, in turn, the commercialization potential of ZIHFB.

In this study, we aim to provide closer insight into the phenomena related to the voltaic bulge. By a complex and systematic characterization of the battery single-cell incl. postmortem analysis of the battery components, we aim to identify origins of the observed battery behaviour close to critical areal capacity and to propose a realistic degradation mechanism and rational measures which can be applied to enhance battery performance and stability. The study is divided into three parts describing: i) identification of the individual degradation phenomena, ii) testing methods for the mitigation of the degradation process and iii) identification of safe operating conditions providing stable and efficient battery operation. By this approach we have optimized operating conditions of the ZIHFB single-cell only minor voltaic efficiency decrease and capacity decay for more than 70 cycles at 100 mA cm^{-2} with mean CE over 96 % and mean VE over 87%, with almost no capacity decay (mean value 0.02% per cycle).

2. Experimental

2.1 Construction of the flow cell and general condition

ZIHFB characterization was conducted using a single-cell (construction derived from std. lab-cell by Pinflow energy storage, s.r.o.). The single-cell design (see **Figure S1a**) was adjusted for the needs of ZIHFB (i.e., flow field design modification) in cooperation with Pinflow. It consists of aluminium end plates, copper current collectors, composite carbon-polymer plates, graphite felts (GFs, rayon-based), elastomeric polyolefin-based flat gaskets, electrolyte distribution frames made of PVC, and activated CEM. GF was activated according to Mazúr et al. [32] and compression ratio (CR) was set to 25%. The geometric area of the electrodes was 20 cm^2 ($4 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$). Flow-through distribution of electrolyte was used for both half-cell compartments.

The standard apparatus (see **Figure S1c**) for the characterization under ZIHFB consist of a peristaltic pump (Watson–Marlow 323), two separate electrolyte tanks and PTFE tubing connecting the tanks to the cell. In the standard characterization negolyte tank contained 0.07 dm³ and posolyte 0.08 dm³ of an electrolyte solution composed of 1 mol dm⁻³ ZnI₂, 4 mol dm⁻³ KI and 1.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl. In some experiments, different volumes of electrolytes with the same composition were used, which is clearly marked at a corresponding experiment. In other one, posolyte was used without Zn²⁺ ions, so the composition was following: 4 mol dm⁻³ KI and 1.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl. The flow rate of both electrolytes was set to 0.08 dm³ min⁻¹. The entire testing apparatus was placed in a temperature-insulated box maintained at a given temperature of 40 °C.

The standard experimental apparatus was extended by adding pressure sensors to monitor the pressure drop in the negative half-cell of ZIHFB (**Figure S1d**) during experiments. The OCV cell (Pinflow energy storage s.r.o.), containing PPG 86 carbon-polymer composite electrodes (Eisenhuth) and suitable CEM, was positioned at the outlet of the main cell to monitor the battery state of charge (SoC) during the entire experiment. An additional 5 voltage probes were used to monitor: open circuit voltage on the OCV cell, potential of main battery electrodes vs. corresponding reference electrodes, and open circuit potential (OCP) of OCV battery electrodes vs. corresponding reference electrodes. All the potentials were collected with Tevomet TV16 multichannel voltage monitor (Kolibrík.net).

2.1.1 Construction modifications of ZIHFB

To investigate the mechanism of irreversible battery performance deterioration, two different strategies were tested: i) a hydraulic connection between the electrolyte tanks (short hydraulic shunt, HS, by thin capillary positioned on bottom of both tanks), to maintain same levels of both electrolytes during the experiment; ii) combination of electronically conductive GF and NCF (polymeric non-conductive felt, FINET PES 1 mm, MITOP) in each half-cell (see **Figure S2**).

2.2 Electrochemical characterization of ZIHFB

For the characterization of ZIHFB single-cell we used a complex procedure consisting of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling combined with constant voltage discharge using battery cycler BSC-815 (Biologic). In the monitoring apparatus Tevomet TV16 multichannel voltage monitor was added (Kolibrík.net), which enabled on-line monitoring of the potentials and pressure drop measurements. Each characterization procedure was slightly different; thus, we will divide this chapter to more sub-chapters.

2.2.1 Standard ZIHFB characterization

Firstly, ZIHFB was cycled in SoC range 0-20% (SoC of negolyte), several cycles were performed, consequently SoC range was increased by 20% (i.e., 0-40% SoC range), this was repeated with stepwise increasing of charging SoC range by 20% in each step till battery was cycled in range 0-80% of the theoretical capacity of the 0.07 dm³ of negolyte. In this article, we will refer SoC as the ratio of the current charged capacity to the theoretical capacity of the negolyte, which corresponds to the total amount of Zn²⁺ ions. Battery was always charged galvanostatically (CC) at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻² to a chosen SoC limit and back-discharged in a combined galvanostatic-potentiostatic (CC-CV) mode with 0.1 V discharging voltage limit till the discharged

current decreased below 10% of the charging current. Subsequently, several dozen cycles were performed with the charging SoC limit of 80%. From the charge-discharge cycling the efficiencies (*CE*, *VE* and *EE*) and capacity utilization (*CU*) were evaluated according to std. relations [32] together with their mean values from each SoC range. *CU* was calculated with respect to the theoretical capacity of the negolyte according to Faraday's law.

2.2.2 Detailed ZIHFB characterization

Detailed battery characterization was done using two different modes of EIS measurement. In the first case, the battery was gradually charged in steps with varying capacities (around area of interest, the capacity of the step was 1.5 mAh cm^{-2}) and between each step, EIS at OCV (further referred to as PEIS_{OCV}) was measured in a potentiostatic mode, frequency ranging from 10 kHz to 25 mHz with a sinus amplitude of perturbing signal of 20 mV. This was done using battery cyler BSC-815 (Biologic). In the second case, EIS was measured under a constant current density load (100 mA cm^{-2}) in a galvanostatic mode (marked GEIS_{LOAD}) in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 50 mHz with a multi-sin regime and the amplitude of perturbing signal of 12.5 mA cm^{-2} . This was done with a potentiostat VSP-3e (Biologic) enabling measurements in a broader frequency range. Since the EIS was measured under current load, battery was continuously charged (or discharged) during the impedance measurement.

From the EIS experiments the values of area specific resistances (*ASRs*) were evaluated; the ohmic *ASR* (*ASR_Ω*) and charge transfer *ASR* (*ASR_{CT}*) by fitting the EIS spectra to suitable equivalent circuit model (for equivalent circuit, see **Figure S3**).

2.2.3 Strategies for capacity regeneration and stable operation of ZIHFB

Rest of the experiments consisted of the electrochemical characterization techniques mentioned above. Volumes of electrolytes can differ, or some construction modifications were realized (i.e., HS of electrolyte tanks or NCF implementation into the cell), which has been described in the **chapter 2.1.1**.

2.3 Microstructure analysis of negative electrodes

Microstructure of the selected GF with deposited zinc was studied by micro-computed tomography (μ CT, sample size $50 \times 40 \times 5.5 \text{ mm}$). The samples were scanned using an X-ray microtomograph, CT portable 160.90 (Fraunhofer). An accelerating voltage of 90 kV was used for the scanning, and 3500 images were taken for each scan with a resolution of 13 microns/pixel and an exposure time of 450 ms/image. The total scanning time was five hours per sample. The resulting structure was obtained from the captured images by mathematical reconstruction in the native software of the microtomograph.

2.4 Pressure half-cell tightness test

To assess the tightness of the battery half-cell, pressure decay test was carried out in a specialized set-up (see **Figure S4**). One of the half-cells was pressurized by nitrogen applying a selected overpressure (in the range of 100-600 mBar), then the hydraulic circuit was closed, and a decay of the internal pressure was monitored by the pressure sensor. The internal tightness of battery was assets from slope of pressure decrease in time evaluated from the 5-minute interval measurement.

3. Results

The primary aim of this study was to get better insight into the phenomena which are taking place during the operation of ZIHFB, particularly during its charging at increased Q_{areal} , leading to irreversible degradation of the battery performance. The result section is divided into the three parts: i) identification of the individual degradation phenomena, ii) testing methods for the mitigation of the degradation process and iii) identification of safe operating conditions providing stable and efficient battery performance at mid-term time scale.

3.1 Voltaic bulge

3.1.1 Existence of voltaic bulge in ZIHFB

Within this section we describe experiments where ZIHFB single-cell was cycled with stepwise increasing SoC charging limit (20-80% of the theoretical capacity of the negolyte, volume of 0.07 mol dm^{-3}) in order to assess the maximum Q_{areal} providing efficient and stable operation. Subsequently, several dozen charge-discharge cycles were performed with 80% SoC charging limit.

First, at low SoC charging limits (20 and 40% SOC) the battery achieved high efficiencies (see **Table 1**), CE above 98% and EE above 85% at the applied current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} . EE started to decrease during cycling with 60% SoC charging limit, but the CE still remained above 98%. The decrease of the EE was primarily caused by increasing charging voltage around Q_{areal} of 100 mAh cm^{-2} (approx. 50% SoC of negolyte). When increasing charging limit to 80% SoC ($\sim 150 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2}$) a sharp increase of the cell voltage appeared followed by its sudden drop, demonstrating as a “voltaic bulge” around 125 mAh cm^{-2} (see **Figure 1a**). After the bulge, charging voltage remains relatively high, around 1.5 V till the end of the charging half-cycle. Interestingly, the initial discharge voltage was about 100 mV lower than for 60% SOC charging limit. CE of the cycle significantly dropped by 9% (CU also decreases correspondingly) when compared to lower charging SoC limits. As visible from **Figure 1a** an available discharge capacity is only slightly higher than the value corresponding to the position of the end of the bulge on the x-axis, even when discharging potentiostatically at low cell voltage of 0.1 V, indicating some irreversible processes taking place during the charging. During the subsequent battery cycling within the same SOC range, the voltaic bulge gradually disappeared (see **Figure 1b, c**), nonetheless, CE continuously decreased from 85% to 70% (see **Figure 1d**). Additionally, we observed a frayed charging voltage profile, which appears at the bulge position, indicating an internal short circuit of the battery (see **Figure 1c**). The observed CE decay can be, to some extent, caused by a change of electrolytes composition and volume due to the observed net-flow through the CEM by osmosis and electro-osmosis (detailed fluxes in our ZIHFB is described further in this chapter). However, the main cause of performance deterioration is most likely linked to the failure of inner cell components.

Table 1: Mean efficiencies and capacity utilization values. **Experimental conditions:** electrolyte: $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ ZnI}_2$, $4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KI}$ and $1.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KCl}$ (0.07 dm^3 negolyte, 0.08 dm^3 posolyte), operating temperature $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, electrolyte flow rate $0.08 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$.

SOC charging limit	Number of cycles	Coulombic Efficiency	Voltaic Efficiency	Energy Efficiency	Capacity utilization
20% SoC	5	99.1 %	84.5 %	83.7 %	20 %
40% SoC	5	98.8 %	85.4 %	84.4 %	40 %
60% SoC	5	98.7 %	78.4 %	77.4 %	59 %
80% SoC	5	89.4 %	76.4 %	68.2 %	72 %
80% SoC	49	77.0 %	78.0 %	60.0 %	67 %

Figure 1: a) ZIHFB voltage dependence on Q_{areal} for 60% and 80% SoC charging limit; Subsequent battery cycling (49 cycles) with 80% SoC charging limit; b) Detail on the voltage development; c) Voltage on Q_{areal} comparing charging of 1st and last cycle with noticeable voltage fraying (here noticeable from approx. 1.33 V). d) Evolution of efficiencies and CU. **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte composition: 1 mol dm^{-3} ZnI_2 , 4 mol dm^{-3} KI and 1.5 mol dm^{-3} KCl (0.07 dm^3 negolyte, 0.08 dm^3 posolyte); Operating temperature: 40 °C; Electrolyte flow rate: 0.08 $\text{dm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$.

In a ZIHFB employing a CEM, potassium ions serve as the primary charge carriers. During charging, K^+ ions, accompanied by their hydration shells, migrate from the posolyte to the negolyte under the influence of the electric field (i.e., migration). Migration, together with electro-osmotic water transport, compensates for the consumption of zinc ions at the negative electrode due to zinc deposition. A minor flux of zinc ions from the posolyte to the negolyte may also occur; however, this contribution is significantly smaller because zinc ions exhibit lower mobility. At the positive electrode, iodide ions are oxidized to tri-iodide, which increases the net positive charge of the posolyte and further drives K^+ migration toward the negolyte. Iodide ions may diffuse from the negolyte to the posolyte to compensate for their consumption, whereas tri-iodide ions tend to diffuse in the opposite direction. Nevertheless, the transport of both iodide and tri-iodide ions is strongly suppressed by the CEM due to its high selectivity and Donnan exclusion. Water transport occurs predominantly from the posolyte to the negolyte, driven by both electro-osmotic drag associated with K^+ migration and osmotic pressure differences arising from compositional changes during charging (schematics of all fluxes is captured on **Figure S1b**). Although all fluxes theoretically reverse during discharge, complete compensation of species transport is rarely achieved in practice. The extent of reversal strongly depends on operating conditions, including the ratio of charging to discharging current densities (which governs migration), the duration of idle periods, and the state of charge (SoC) of the electrolytes during these pauses. Consequently, the volumes of the negolyte and posolyte change dynamically during battery operation. Importantly, because charging is not perfectly efficient (coulombic efficiency $< 100\%$), the net ionic and water flux through the CEM is biased toward the charging direction. Over extended cycling, this imbalance leads to progressive electrolyte overflow and volume accumulation in the negolyte compartment.

3.1.2 Structural analysis of negative 3D electrode

When analysing the negative electrode for the std. deposition to 80% SoC, i.e., after the 1st charging (negolyte volume of 0.07 dm³, Q_{areal} of 150 mAh cm⁻²), the zinc was found to be deposited on both sides of the GF, i.e., on the side facing the current collector (see **Figure S5b**) as well as on the side facing the membrane (see **Figure 2a**). The zinc distribution within the GF obtained via μ CT characterization (see **Figure 2b, c**) confirmed that Zn is dominantly deposited on the membrane side of the GF. Zn was, to a minor extent, deposited also within the collector side of GF, probably due to initially high contact resistance of the carbon composite/GF interface, which was gradually reduced by the deposited Zn in the initial phase of the charging.

Figure 2: a) Photography of GF covered with zinc on the membrane side; μ CT reconstruction in b) z- and c) x-direction showing the Zn distribution within GF electrode.

The preferential Zn distribution close to the membrane is due to fact that the electronic path within the GF is by order of magnitude more conductive (1100 mS cm^{-1} [33], depending on the relative compression) when compared to ionic conductivity of the electrolyte (300 mS cm^{-1}). Thus, electric charge is preferentially transported in form of electrons to the membrane proximity where it is transfer from carbon fibres to an electrolyte via electrochemical reaction (Zn deposition). As expected, more zinc is deposited at the inlet of the GF due to the higher local concentration of reactants in the inlet region, which are being gradually consumed by the charging reaction. More importantly, excessive Zn deposition on the membrane side of GF gradually decreases the effective area available for ionic transport through the membrane (required for maintaining the electrolytes electroneutrality). For expected ionic fluxes during the battery charging, see discussion in **chapter 3.1.1**.

At a certain Q_{areal} the transport of the ions becomes limited by the created compact zinc layer on the GF-membrane interface and thus the overpotential of the cell steeply increases. Once the peak of overvoltage is achieved, the voltage starts to decrease, which is most probably caused by gradual piercing of the IEM by Zn dendrites which are growing from the compact Zn layer towards the positive electrode. Interestingly, the cell voltage does not drop to zero (or close to this value), which would be expected for the short-circuited cell, but it only decreases to a value slightly below 1.5 V. This can be explained by immediate exposure of zinc dendrites to tri-iodide ions (generated during the charging in the positive half-cell) which effectively dissolves these temporary shorts. This so-called self-healing effect in ZIHFB has been described by Xie et al. [29] as a gradual

dissolution of the zinc growing through the porous separator. In the cell configuration using a porous separator, this self-healing effect can potentially prevent the battery failure by a short-circuit as the separator's properties are probably much less degraded by the growing Zn, most probably due to relatively large pores size. In contrast, for a cell using homogenous IEM, the growing Zn dendrites can pierce the thin polymeric film resulting in the membrane perforation and its gradual performance degradation. In this case, the presence of tri-iodide ions in posolyte has no longer self-healing effect as was reported for cells using porous separator.

3.2 Detailed study of voltaic bulge

To further investigate the origins of the voltaic bulge, the reference electrodes were positioned on the outlet of both half-cells, which enabled on-line monitoring of both electrodes' potentials during the battery testing (the potentials were recalculated to the normal hydrogen electrode NHE). In **Figure S6**, we can see that during the battery charging in the capacity region of the voltaic bulge, the electrode potentials showed only a minor change in the trend, not proportional to the observed trend in the cell voltage. This can be illustrated from difference between yellow curve (measured cell voltage) and a purple curve representing the difference between both electrodes' potentials. This suggests that the increased cell overvoltage is linked with some processes related to the IEM rather than electrodes.

At first, we had to confirmed that the presence of voltaic bulge is not a function of electrolyte SoC (i.e., composition). Thus, we have repeated the same cycling experiment but with decreased amount of the electrolytes. On **Figure 3a** we compare development of the cell voltage during a charge-discharge cycle for two negolyte volumes: i) our standard electrolyte volume of 0.07 dm³ (Q_{areal} of 188 mAh cm⁻²) and; ii) decreased volume of 0.05 dm³ (Q_{areal} of 134 mAh cm⁻²). With decreased negolyte volume we observed no signs of the voltaic bulge when charging to the same SoC limit (80% of the negolyte's theoretical capacity). In **Figure 3b**, we compare ohmic and charge transfer $ASRs$ evaluated from EIS measurements performed within these experiments. We can see that at the beginning of the charging, ASR_{Ω} slightly decreases for both negolyte volumes, but furthermore, significant increase of ASR_{CT} occurs only for the standard (higher) negolyte volume. In contrast, with the lower negolyte volume, there is only a minor ASR_{CT} increase at the really end of the charging. In **Figure 3c**, we can see that, for lower negolyte volume, both $ASRs$ remain almost constant during whole discharge period and only close to the end of discharge they started to grow. For standard negolyte volume the development of ASR is significantly different and will be further discussed within this chapter.

Figure 3: **a)** ZIHFB voltage dependence on Q_{areal} within a charge-discharge cycle for two different electrolyte volumes with the same 80% SoC charging limit; ASR_{CT} and ASR_{Ω} evaluated from $GEIS_{LOAD}$ measured during the battery: **b)** charging and **c)** discharging phase of the cycle. **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte composition: 1 mol dm⁻³ ZnI₂, 4 mol dm⁻³ KI and 1.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl (electrolyte volumes 0.05 dm³ and 0.07 dm³); Operating temperature: 40 °C; Electrolyte flow rate: 0.08 dm³ min⁻¹.

Detailed characterization of the voltaic bulge for std. electrolyte volume was carried out by a stepwise charging, where between each charging step (approx. 1.5 mAh cm⁻² within the region of the voltaic bulge) the PEIS_{OCV} was measured. In the **Figure 4a** we can see that charging voltage in the region of the bulge is significantly higher when compared to the standard charging (i.e., CC charging without frequent EIS measurements), while the discharged capacity is even further decreased resulting in *CE* of only 70%. This is probably due to longer pauses between charge and discharge part of the cycle (each PEIS_{OCV} required more than 10 minutes, i.e., whole charge-discharge cycle took more than 13 hours, while STD one only 3 hours). Interestingly, for a given Q_{areal} (i.e., electrolyte SOC) we observed significant variation of the EIS spectra in time (see **Figure S7**). This is most probably linked with the surface passivation of zinc deposited at negative electrode; however, more detailed study is needed to confirm the hypothesis, which is beyond the scope of our study. Additionally, quality of EIS spectra was significantly decreased at higher Q_{areal} (specifically at low frequencies region), most probably due to insufficient stability of the system. Due to these reasons, the PEIS_{OCV} characterization was found unsuitable for our purposes. Interestingly, we observed drop of OCV_{Cell}, although relatively small (approx. 14 mV), starting at

the Q_{areal} corresponding to the voltage bulge peak, suggesting changes in the composition of the electrolyte and/or electrodes as shown in **Figure 4b**. The observed decrease in OCV_{Cell} can be attributed to the membrane damage, which allows direct exposure of the deposited zinc to the polysolte containing tri-iodides, leading to enhanced self-discharge. However, since the majority of zinc electrode remain intact and the bulk negolyte composition is largely preserved, the overall change in OCV remains rather small.

Figure 4: a) Comparison of different characterization techniques STD, PEIS_{OCV} and GEIS_{LOAD} for ZIHFB. b) OCV_{Cell} dependence on Q_{areal} during PEIS_{OCV} characterization. c) ZIHFB voltage dependence on Q_{areal} during GEIS_{LOAD}

characterization with evaluated ASR_{CT} and ASR_{Ω} , colours used in the voltage cell evolution is linked to the **d**) where EIS spectra are displayed with colour for corresponding Q_{areal} . Figures **e**) and **f**) represents the same as **c** and **d**, but for battery discharge. **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte composition: 1 mol dm⁻³ ZnI₂, 4 mol dm⁻³ KI and 1.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl (electrolytes volumes 0.07 dm³); Operating temperature 40 °C; Electrolyte flow rate 0.08 dm³ min⁻¹.

To mitigate the influence of battery behaviour instability during PEIS_{OCV} measurements, GEIS_{LOAD} was performed under constant current density load. **Figure 4a** compares the cell voltage profiles for standard (STD) charging, PEIS_{OCV}, and GEIS_{LOAD}. The overvoltage development observed during GEIS_{LOAD} closely resembles that of STD charging conditions. However, the voltaic bulge appeared even at lower Q_{areal} . The sooner presence of the bulge may be attributed to the alternating current applied during the GEIS measurement (i.e., current densities oscillated around 100 mA cm⁻²). Nevertheless, the bulge's position varies slightly across the measurements, for the std. conditions typically occurring between 115 and 130 mAh cm⁻², thus both STD and GEIS_{LOAD} experiments can be considered as comparable.

More importantly, a significant increase in the ASR_{CT} is observed for GEES measurement (see **Figure 4c, d**), beginning around 130 mAh cm⁻². The ASR_{CT} peak position is in accordance with the overvoltage maximum and subsequently decreases, stabilizing at approximately 1 Ω cm². In contrast, ASR_{Ω} gradually decreases in the same Q_{areal} region, with the most pronounced drop occurring near the voltage peak, after which it remains relatively constant. The decreased ASR_{Ω} aligns well with the hypothesis of the membrane being pierced by Zn dendrites and its gradual damage under these conditions.

Interestingly, the presence of voltaic bulge does also affect the battery overvoltage at the beginning of subsequent discharging. **Figure 4e** shows a significant drop of battery voltage during initial discharging phase, caused by the increase of ASR_{Ω} (compared to the ASR_{Ω} at the end of charging), probably due to zinc electrode passivation (by tri-iodide ions). During the subsequent battery discharging ASR_{Ω} decreases back to 0.6 Ω cm² after approx. 25 mAh cm⁻² and, further on, the discharge voltage is similar to the experiment with the lower volume (see **Figure 3a**). ASR_{CT} increases when the battery is almost fully discharged i.e., zinc is almost fully dissolved.

To test the integrity of the membrane after the cycling a tightness test was applied (after it was emptied). One of the half-cells of the ZIHFB was pressurized by nitrogen, then hydraulically closed and the rate of its pressure decay was monitored. In an initial cell with a fresh membrane, the pressure decayed at a slow rate of approx. 0.01 mbar s⁻¹ even under an overpressure of 600 mbar. In contrast, for the cell after the performed experiments we observed significantly faster pressure drops of 0.32 mbar s⁻¹, indicating a decreased tightness of the membrane, most probably due to its perforation by Zn dendrites.

3.2.1 Influence of electrolyte composition: ZnI₂ omission in posolyte

To further deepen our insight into the phenomena related to voltaic bulge we performed a similar set of experiments, but with ZnI₂ omitted from the posolyte. In the experiment where EIS was measured under steady-state conditions (PEIS_{OCV}), we observed that the battery voltage increased earlier approx. at 100 mAh cm⁻² and a sudden voltage drop occurred later (purple curve in **Figure 5a**) compared to the standard operation (black curve). Moreover, the OCV behaviour also differed: instead of stabilizing, the OCV continued to rise and only dropped when the overvoltage decreased

(see **Figure 5b**). Since Zn^{2+} ions were absent in the posolyte for this experiment, they could not be supplied to the negative half-cell during the charging, unlike in the standard electrolyte set-up. At higher Q_{areal} , when the GF begins to be plated with a compact zinc layer and ion transport to the electrode surface becomes limited, the additional supply of Zn^{2+} from the posolyte is thus missing. Presence of a compact zinc layer barrier limits the K^+ transport between the half-cells which results in a premature voltage increase in case of PEIS_{OCV} experiment.

However, in case of cycling with EIS measurements under the load ($\text{GEIS}_{\text{LOAD}}$) the absence of Zn^{2+} in the posolyte appears to delay the voltage drop, shifting it to higher Q_{areal} values, see **Figure 5a**, where the voltage bulge appears at significantly higher Q_{areal} ($\sim 150 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2}$) comparing to the standard operation. While the ASR_{Ω} remains approximately constant at the onset of the bulge, ASR_{CT} sharply grows in this region. However, ASR_{CT} does not decrease significantly with the voltage drop – only its slight reduction is observed. This behaviour can be explained by partial membrane penetration by Zn dendrites (reflected in the decreased ASR_{Ω}) and partial zinc dissolution by tri-iodide ions. However, since Zn^{2+} are absent in the posolyte, the Zn deposition cannot proceed in the positive half-cell, as it was possible for standard electrolyte configuration and thus ASR_{CT} does not decrease. Overall, the absence of Zn^{2+} in the posolyte allows to achieve higher Q_{areal} and reduces discharge overvoltage. At the same time, however, different initial composition of the posolyte and negolyte would inevitably lead to the earlier battery failure. This is primarily due to a significant cross-over of water, active species and other ions through the CEM, which gradually changes the electrolytes composition (demonstrated on **Figure S8**). The fluxes for symmetrical electrolyte composition is discussed in **chapter 3.1.1**. In principle, the flux behaviour in this modified configuration will remain similar; however, because Zn^{2+} is absent in the posolyte, the compensating flux of K^+ ions through the CEM will be even greater leading to the more significant disbalance. In case of std. electrolytes, the initial electrolyte composition can be in principle easily recovered by simple remixing of the electrolytes. For the posolyte without ZnI_2 this measure is no longer possible.

c)

d)

Figure 5: **a)** Comparison of different characterization techniques STD, PEIS_{OCV} and GEIS_{LOAD} for ZIHFB. with omitted zinc ions in posolyte. **b)** OCV_{Cell} dependence on Q_{areal} during PEIS_{OCV} characterization. **c)** ZIHFB voltage dependence on Q_{areal} during GEIS_{LOAD} characterization with evaluated ASR_{CT} and ASR_{Ω} , colours used in the voltage cell evolution is linked to the **d)** where EIS spectra are displayed with colour for corresponding Q_{areal} . Figures **e)** and **f)** represents the same as **c)** and **d)**, but for battery discharge. **Experimental conditions:** Negolyte composition: 1 mol dm⁻³ ZnI₂, 4 mol dm⁻³ KI and 1.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl (electrolytes volumes 0.07 dm³), ZnI₂ was omitted in posolyte everything else remained the same; Operating temperature 40 °C; Electrolyte flow rate 0.08 dm³ min⁻¹.

3.3 Strategies for capacity regeneration

Subsequently, with the degraded battery we tested several strategies that are typically used for a RFB to restore its initial capacity, namely: i) electrolyte remix, ii) exchange of both electrolytes for the fresh ones and iii) exchange of the CEM (while keeping same electrolytes). In this series of experiments the volume of electrolyte were decreased to 0.06 dm³.

Electrolyte remixing

First strategy tested for regenerating the battery performance was mixing the posolyte and negolyte and redistributing them. This procedure for regenerating the initial composition of the electrolytes is possible thanks to the identical initial composition of both electrolytes. The electrolyte mixing procedure was performed after the batteries were fully discharged (i.e., after combined galvanostatic discharge with potentiostatic retention at a voltage of 0.1 V). Subsequently, the outlet tubes connecting the individual half-cells to the respective electrolyte reservoirs were interchanged, and in this arrangement, the electrolytes were intensively mixed (30 min) in order to achieve full equalization of their composition and possible additional complete dissolution of

zinc residues in the negative half-cell by their reaction with tri-iodide ion residues contained in the posolyte. Subsequently, the outlet tubes were reconnected to the respective reservoirs, the electrolytes were distributed in the equal volume ratio to the respective reservoirs. During the subsequent battery cycling after electrolytes remix, CE remained low, even for lower SoC charging limits (started from 40% SoC, see (see **Figure 6a**). Interestingly, in the first cycle after the electrolyte remix, we can observe the low charging voltage i.e., short plateau at 0.1 V at the beginning of charging, (0 - 5 mAh cm⁻², see **Figure S9**), which was caused by the reduction of tri-iodide ions at negative half-cell. The tri-iodide presence in the remixed negolyte was a consequence of faradaic imbalance between both electrolytes before the remix due to the coulombic inefficiency of the negative half-cell reaction (HER side reaction, self-discharge due to Zn corrosion) and cumulating of tri-iodide ions in the posolyte tank. Even after a complete electrolyte exchange for the fresh electrolytes (see **Figure 6a**), the original CE was not restored, which indicate a CEM damage.

Membrane exchange

To confirm the CEM damage, we repeated the experiment described above. The procedure involved initially increasing the SoC until the characteristic voltaic bulge reappeared. Following this, the battery was fully discharged, and the electrolyte was remixed, as previously outlined. Then the used CEM was replaced with a fresh one, while leaving the rest of the battery components unchanged (incl. GFs and both electrolytes). In **Figure 6b** we can see that the CEM replacement led to a substantial recovery of the CE to 90%, clearly proving that the membrane degradation is mostly responsible for cell performance degradation related to voltage bulge. However, during initial cycles the CE dropped again, as already in the second cycle the voltaic bulge was observed (despite the charging voltage cut-off limit set to 1.55 V), resulting in CEM damaged and gradual discharge capacity decrease. Lower CU after electrolyte exchange was caused by presence of tri-iodide ions in remixed negolyte.

Figure 6: **a)** Efficiencies and CU for the experiment in with remix of the electrolyte and exchange of the electrolytes. **b)** Efficiencies and CU for the experiment in with CEM exchange. **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte composition: 1 mol dm⁻³ ZnI₂, 4 mol dm⁻³ KI and 1.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl (electrolytes volumes 0.06 dm³); Operating temperature 40 °C; Electrolyte flow rate 0.08 dm³ min⁻¹.

3.4 Construction modifications

Based on our findings that the voltaic bulge is caused by deposition of compact zinc layer close to the IEM and consequent perforation of CEM by Zn dendrites, we have tested several protection construction modifications of battery cell and experimental set-up to mitigate the unwanted degradation mechanism aiming to increase Q_{areal} securing stable and efficient operation of ZIHFB.

3.4.1 Non-conductive felt

Kellamis et al. [21] used NCF to increase the Q_{areal} of the ZIHFB operation. We focused on similar approach by combination of electronically conductive GF and NCF (polymeric non-conductive felt, FINET PES 1 mm, MITOP) in each half-cell, separately, in order to see the effect of this construction modification on the cell behaviour at increased Q_{areal} aiming to at least partially suppress this phenomenon or to shift it to the higher Q_{areal} . The NCF was always located in a direct contact with the CEM, which was supposed to provide better protection of the membrane against Zn dendrites (for detailed schematics see **Figure S2**).

Initially, the combination of GF and NCF (close to membrane) was used in the negative battery half-cell (for short NCF_{NEG}), aiming to shift the initial deposition zone farer from the membrane. Surprisingly, the use of NCF_{NEG} reduced CE by 3-4 % for all tested charging SoC limits (see **Figure 7a**), when compared to std. battery construction (i.e., both GF was conductive). This is probably a consequence of preferential pathways for deposition of Zn in the NCF_{NEG} structure where, due to the relatively high applied current density (100 mA cm^{-2}), Zn is unevenly deposited (negative electrode after cycling is shown in **Figure S10**) forming undesirable dendritic structures that are more susceptible to parasitic processes such as hydrogen evolution, Zn passivation and physical disintegration from electrode bulk. Thus, contrary to our expectations, the application of NCF in the negative half-cell did not lead to the desired suppression of the occurrence of the voltaic bulge, nor to its shift to higher Q_{areal} .

Figure 7: **a)** CE evolution for the standard construction and the experiment with the NCF_{NEG} and NCF_{POS} half-cell in the ZIHFB. **b)** Comparison of voltage evolution for different construction modification at 80% SoC. **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte composition: $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ ZnI}_2$, $4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KI}$ and $1.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KCl}$ (0.07 dm^3 negolyte, 0.08 dm^3 posolyte); operating temperature $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; flow rate of electrolyte $0.08 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$.

A possible explanation for the voltaic bulge presence in the case of NCF_{NEG} is that a compact layer of zinc grows near the GF/NCF interface, which may have a similar insulating effect for ions

transport between both half-cells of battery, increasing local current densities in turn resulting in more pronounced zinc dendrites formation and CEM perforation. Interestingly, the decreased voltage at the beginning of the discharge step is considerably shorter when compared to std. cell construction, which can be attributed to the fact that the compact zinc layer is located on the GF/NCF interface (i.e., not in a direct contact with CEM) and thus smaller portion of CEM cross-sectional area is blocked. Higher discharge voltage is demonstrated on increased VE by 5%. The voltaic bulge position occurs at approx. same Q_{areal} (i.e., 125 mAh cm⁻²) as for std. electrode configuration suggesting that maximal capacity is limited by inner geometry of cell rather than distribution of conductive and non-conductive phases.

In the next experiment, a NCF was used in a positive half-cell (again facing the membrane, for short NCF_{POS}). The voltaic bulge was present in ZIHFB with NCF_{POS} (see **Figure 7b**) even though it was not that significant, the position of it was similar to the STD and NCF_{NEG} and irreversible reduction of the battery CE was also observed. The initial drop in discharge voltage was similar to that observed under standard operating conditions, indicating that this effect is associated with the negative half-cell, as the only structural modification was made on the positive side. In contrast, this voltage drop was absent in the NCF_{NEG} configuration, further supporting this conclusion. Due to the presence of a NCF_{POS} near the CEM, it can be argued that the irreversibly reduced CE is not caused by the std. internal battery short circuit, i.e., the electron-conductive connection of the two electrodes. More probably, the zinc growing through the membrane is being continuously dissolved by the I₃⁻ present in the posolyte, and this self-discharging process leads to a decreased CE , and its further gradual decrease due to the membrane perforation by Zn dendrites (after whose dissolution holes remain in the membrane). Alternatively, some of the I₃⁻ may penetrate through these pores and dissolve the zinc deposited in the negative half-cell.

Table 2 shows a generally lower VE and EE of the NCF_{POS} cell due to the significant increase in ASR_{Ω} (EIS measured at 50% SoC) caused by the presence of the electronically insulating NCF. Interestingly, for the NCF_{NEG} experiment, such significant increase in ASR_{Ω} was not observed, as upon the charging zinc is present within the negative electrodes structure (both in GF and NCF), which compensates the reduced conductivity of the NCF layer. Initial charging overvoltage for both NCF experiments is similar, and it decreases with increasing Q_{areal} for the arrangement with NCF_{NEG}, which confirms that the deposited zinc compensates increased ohmic resistance.

Table 2: ASR_{Ω} in 50% of the SoCs and evaluated average CE , VE .

	ASR_{Ω}	CE SoC 60 %	VE SoC 60 %	CE SoC 80 %	VE SoC 80 %
	$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	%	%	%	%
Standard	0.68	98.7	78.4	89.4	76.4
NCF _{NEG}	0.60	94.3	83.4	83.4	81.1
NCF _{POS}	1.54	96.1	70.9	85	69.6

Despite similar construction modifications used (NCF_{POS}) as in case of Kellamis et al. [21], we did not achieve increase of Q_{areal} . This can be attributed to our use of much more conductive GF which likely caused zinc deposition closer to the CEM and thus earlier battery failure. Another factors such as use of different electrolyte composition (they used ZnCl₂ and NH₄Br) may cause the difference. Additionally, if we look on the Kellamis et al. results we can see that during the initial 10 cycles available Q_{areal} decreased by more than 170 mAh cm⁻² from the original 490 mAh cm⁻², due to the significant increase of charging voltage and presence of zinc oxide in negative half-cell. Thus, a similar trend was observed as in our system: a significant increase in charging voltage consequently affecting the discharge voltage. Nevertheless, the battery was not permanently damaged, likely due to the implementation of a safety charging voltage limit.

3.4.2 Hydraulic connection of electrolyte tanks

Finally, we have identified stable operating conditions for the ZIHFB system by combining a safety charging cut-off voltage and a reduced capacity limit with a hydraulic connection between the electrolyte tanks (HS). HS was used to maintain equal electrolytes volumes and to at least partially equalize their composition via a thin capillary on the bottom of the tanks. This strategy is typically use in VRFB to mitigate capacity decay. Uneven vanadium ion permeation (direction depends on IEM type) across membranes causes a concentration imbalance, leading to osmotic water flow toward the electrolyte with higher vanadium concentration resulting in increased volume (i.e. composition of electrolytes changes). In systems with a hydraulic shunt, electrolyte volumes are equalized, reducing composition imbalance. However, this also causes self-discharge due to synproportionation of vanadium ions, lowering coulombic efficiency [34]. In a ZIHFB with a CEM, the net ion and water flux during charging is directed from the posolyte to the negolyte, reversing during discharge, as discussed in **Section 3.1.1**. When a (HS) is present, the reverse flow through the HS partially compensates for these volume changes and, to some extent, mitigates composition imbalances during operation. However, this benefit comes at the cost of reduced capacity due to self-discharge. Specifically, tri-iodide ions can migrate through the HS to the negolyte during discharge, where they chemically oxidize zinc, leading to zinc dissolution. While this dissolution can help prevent excessive zinc accumulation and associated risks, it may also cause significant capacity loss and a reduction in cell potential over time.

A cycling protocol with 10 CC cycles followed by two CC–CV regeneration cycles (CV cut-off voltage 0.1 V) was deployed, ensuring full discharge of the negative half-cell and complete zinc dissolution. To secure safe operating condition during the mid-term cycling stability, the charging limit was limited to 50% (negolyte volume 0.06 dm³, Q_{areal} of 80 mAh cm⁻²), i.e., safely below the critical capacity. Charging was terminated either upon reaching this capacity or a cell voltage of 1.55 V.

Firstly, the apparatus without HS of electrolyte tanks was used to study the effect of HS on operation of ZIHFB. Despite safety limits, the operation of the battery without HS construction modification was unstable. As it is shown, the battery operated (without the HS exhibits) a gradual decline in all efficiencies during each CC cycling (see **Figure 8a**), which was probably attributed to the zinc accumulation (its incomplete dissolution), which caused the battery to operate at increasingly higher SoC (of negolyte), leading to increased charging voltage. During the two CC-

CV formatting cycles, a steep increase in CE was observed, indicating that the accumulated zinc was effectively dissolved by potentiostatic discharge at 0.1 V. However, the improvement is only temporary because voltaic bulge appeared (after approx. 48 cycles, 80 hours) and battery was irreversibly degraded. Voltaic bulge probably appeared due to the changing electrolyte composition caused by significant electrolyte cross-over (from posolyte to negolyte, see **Figure S11**).

Deployment of HS (see **Figure 8b**), led to significant stabilization of the battery operation due to continuous balancing of the electrolyte's volumes (and partially also of their composition). Most likely, part of accumulated zinc was also being partially dissolved during discharge by the I_3^- , which were gradually transported to negolyte via HS. It means, that continuous mitigation of zinc accumulation in the negative half-cell prevents overcharging of battery (i.e., exceeding critical Q_{areal}) and protects against subsequent membrane damage. With these optimized conditions ZIHFB was operated at 100 mA cm^{-2} , achieving high performance demonstrated on VE and EE consistently above 80 % while no significant degradation was observed.

Figure 8: Comparison of efficiencies development in ZIHFB under optimized operation conditions **a**) without HS and **b**) with HS. **Experimental conditions:** electrolytes composition: $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ ZnI}_2$, $4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KI}$ and 1.5 mol dm^{-3} (electrolytes volumes 0.06 dm^3), operating temperature $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, flow rate of electrolyte $0.08 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$, charging voltage limit 1.55V and Q_{areal} capacity charge limit 80 mAh cm^{-2} .

We found that from the tested mitigation strategies, the only effective one providing a mid-term stable and efficient battery operation (at least in our configuration) is to limit the maximal charged Q_{areal} , to include a voltage charging limit and, most importantly, to implement HS construction modification for mutual connection of the electrolyte tanks. The achieved Q_{areal} of 80 mAh cm^{-2} at high current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} is higher when compared to most of the literature where the reported Q_{areal} values are between $40\text{-}60 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2}$ [29, 35-37] for current densities no higher than 80 mA cm^{-2} . Only few studies reported higher Q_{areal} (stable above 350 mAh cm^{-2}), such as Kellamis et al. [21] thanks to use of NCF_{POS} , as was discussed in previous chapter. However, our configuration excels in high efficiencies (EE is higher by 24% in our configuration) and improved safety (bromine free) which can be used for power application with lower capacity.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we investigated a degradation phenomenon in ZIHFBS, termed the voltaic bulge, which occurs when charging to high Q_{areal} . This effect manifests as a sharp voltage rise followed by a drop, and although it disappears after a few cycles, it causes irreversible damage to the IEM, requiring replacement. Our results suggest that the bulge originates from the formation of a compact zinc layer near the membrane interface, restricting ionic transport and increasing local current density, which promotes dendrite growth and membrane perforation. The phenomenon typically appears at a critical Q_{areal} of 115–130 mAh cm⁻² and is promoted by Zn²⁺ in the posolyte. Removing Zn²⁺ from the posolyte delays its onset but is not a viable long-term solution due to cross-contamination and early failure. Despite this, optimized operating conditions enabled stable cycling with $CE \geq 95\%$, VE and $EE > 83\%$ at 100 mA cm⁻², and a low-capacity fade of 0.02% per cycle. Understanding this mechanism provides a basis for strategies to mitigate membrane degradation and improve the durability of ZIHFBS and related zinc-based chemistries.

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